

3D-printing of thermoplastic protein-based composites by fused deposition modelling

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ABSTRACT

Proteins can be plasticised to create thermoplastic materials suitable for 3D printing using fused deposition modelling (FDM). This study explores the plasticisation of zein, calcium caseinate, and their blends with glycerol, focusing on their thermal and rheological properties, as well as their performance in 3D printing. Thermoplastic protein-based composites were prepared through a process of protein dissolution, plasticisation, film casting and pelletisation. Calcium caseinate (CaCas) showed good miscibility with glycerol, whereas phase separation was observed in zein-based composites at higher glycerol concentrations. Zein-based pellets were successfully 3D-printed by using a pellet extruder as the printhead. Stable 3D structures were printed without need for post-processing and an unsupported 45° overhang angle was achieved. Calcium caseinate-based pellets were not extrudable using the current setup due to their high viscosity. Furthermore, the thermal and rheological properties of protein composites correlated well with their printing performance. This study showed that protein-based composites are promising materials for FDM applications.

1. Introduction

Additive manufacturing (AM) provides several advantages for small-scale manufacturing, such as fast prototyping and reduced use of materials and energy. Other benefits of AM include large design freedom, direct assembly of multiple components into a single piece and manufacture of components that cannot be produced using subtractive manufacturing methods. For these reasons, AM technologies such as 3D printing have been intensively studied in the fields of food engineering, tissue engineering and robotics (Floresano et al., 2024; Godoi et al., 2016). For example, extrusion-based 3D printing has been employed to manufacture protein-rich food structures such as meat and fish analogues or protein bars from yield-stress materials (Cheng et al., 2025; Shi et al., 2023; Van Der Sman et al., 2024). 3D printed foods could be used to promote healthier eating habits, provide novel gastronomic experiences or provide personalized nutrition and the developed composite materials can potentially be used to 3D print protein-rich food products (Floresano et al., 2024; Venkatachalam et al., 2023). Recently, use of AM to produce edible robotic components such as flexible sensors and actuators has been explored (Choe et al., 2022; Edward and Golecki, 2023; Heiden et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2019).

In fused deposition modelling (FDM) the material is made flowable by heating it above its glass transition temperature (T_g) or melting point (T_m). The material cools and solidifies after deposition, which allows successive deposition of layers and hence creation of 3D structures (Vaes and Van Puyvelde, 2021). Most proteins are thermosetting due to their thermal denaturation behaviour. Some proteins, like zein and caseinate, exhibit thermoplastic behaviour that is comparable to that of traditionally used polymers (e.g. polylactic acid), which make them potential feedstocks for FDM of edible, or bio-compatible materials (Chaurin et al., 2017b).

In this study, we investigate the suitability of casein and zein for FDM. Zein is a byproduct of the extraction of oil and starch from corn meal (Tallawi et al., 2023) and is fully digestible by humans (Kianirad et al., 2021). Due to its excellent biocompatibility, hydrophobic properties and slow dissolution rate it is frequently studied as carrier material for pharmaceutical compounds or as encapsulation material for foods (Bouman et al., 2015; Kasaai, 2018). Casein has traditionally been used not just as a food ingredient, but also as paint and glue. When cross-linked it can be used to make buttons and fibres for textile (Lanital or Aralac). Use of caseinate in packaging materials has been explored as well, as its high density of polar groups makes it a good barrier to

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non-polar substances like oxygen and carbon dioxide (Arrieta et al., 2013; Bonnaille et al., 2014; Chevalier et al., 2018).

Zein has a compact globular structure and casein has a micellar structure, therefore neither protein is prone to unfolding and denaturing upon heating. When heated above their glass transition temperatures the intermolecular bonds are weakened, which is a thermoreversible process. However, both proteins have relatively high glass transition temperatures, and use of the pure proteins for FDM would require heating them near their thermal degradation temperature to achieve sufficient flowability. This can be resolved by incorporating plasticisers, which lower their T_g and reduce the brittleness of thermoplastic materials (Hernandez-Izquierdo and Krochta, 2008). Many chemicals can act as plasticiser, with glycerol being a promising candidate as it is a small, non-volatile molecule. Thus it does not evaporate during FDM. It has been reported that glycerol-plasticised zein can be extruded into an amorphous thermoplastic filament suitable for FDM (Chaunier et al., 2017b). Developing the suitable formulation using blends of zein and casein with plasticiser may yield composites that fall within the window of rheological properties for printability (Oechsle et al., 2016). Recently, Duty et al. (2018), Das et al. (2021) & Sola (2022) provided excellent reviews on evaluating the suitability of a polymer feedstock for FDM. Their frameworks are summarized in the theory section of the current work and utilized to evaluate if our composite materials meet fundamental conditions for successful 3D printing using FDM.

It is hypothesised that the thermorheological properties of a material correlate with its processability and can be tuned through adjusting their composition. To evaluate this, we investigated the effect of the formulation of zein and casein blends in combination with glycerol as a plasticiser. We evaluated their thermorheological properties and 3D printing performance. Modulated differential scanning calorimetry (mDSC) was employed to determine the glass transitions of the composites. Temperature- and shear-dependent complex viscosity of the composites was determined using a closed cavity rheometer (CCR) which can operate at temperatures above 100 °C. A novel processing route was developed to ensure homogeneous composite materials, involving protein dissolution, plasticisation, casting, evaporation and pelletizing. Obtained pellets could be fed directly to a FDM printer. The findings of this research will contribute to the further advancement of FDM using edible, biocompatible materials and the developed composite materials can potentially be used to 3D print protein-rich food products.

2. Theory

2.1. Material requirements in FDM

A material is considered printable if it meets four requirements: (1) it can be extruded out of a nozzle, (2) it can hold its shape after deposition until the next layer is deposited, (3) it is capable of interlayer welding and (4) it remains stable during cooling to ambient temperature (Das et al., 2021; Duty et al., 2018; Sola, 2022).

To meet requirements 1 and 3, the material's viscosity should be approximately 200 Pa s or lower, based on measurements at a shear rate of 100 s⁻¹ which lies within the mid-range of shear rates (30–200 s⁻¹) typically reported for FDM processes (Ajinjeru et al., 2017; Chaunier et al., 2017b, 2018; Das et al., 2021; Gilmer et al., 2018; Spoerk et al., 2017). Furthermore, the extruders feeding mechanism must be able to provide enough force to push the softened material out of the nozzle.

To fulfil requirement 2, a rapid transition in viscosity after extrusion is required: solidification is induced through reduced shear rates and cooling. Typically, plastics utilized in FDM exhibit shear thinning during flow (Sola, 2022). This helps the material solidify as it transitions from the high-temperature, high-shear conditions within the nozzle to the low-shear, low-temperature environment after deposition (Ma et al., 2022). To fulfil requirement 3, newly deposited material should be able

to bond to previously deposited material through molecular diffusion in a viscous-flow sintering process with surface tension as main driving force. There is somewhat of a trade-off between requirement 2 and 3 because viscosity increase after deposition needs to be sufficiently fast for mechanical stability, but slow enough to allow fusing of the printed layers (Chaunier et al., 2018; Heiden et al., 2022). Requirement 4 can be achieved by minimising thermal stresses over the printed object.

One of the major challenges in filament based FDM printing is the production of filaments, which are the most common feedstock for FDM processes. Production of filament requires the material to be processable without thermal degradation. The extruded filament should have a consistent diameter and sufficient bendability for spooling (Sola, 2022). During preliminary testing our composites failed to meet these requirements for the production of filament. FDM processes can also use pellets as feedstock, which are less demanding during pre-processing. Pellet-fed FDM was therefore chosen for this study.

2.2. Thermal-rheological properties of composites

The processability of thermoplastic composite materials during FDM is related to their thermal and rheological properties. In this study, the glass transition temperature (T_g), shear viscosity and viscosity at different temperatures were determined experimentally. Using theoretical models to describe the experimental data can help to understand how composite materials can be optimized for FDM technology (see equations (1)–(3)).

Specifically, shear rate dependency of viscosity can be described by the Ostwald-de Waele power law model (Acierno and Patti, 2023):

$$\eta(\dot{\gamma}) = C \dot{\gamma}^{n-1} \quad (1)$$

With η the viscosity (Pa•s), $\dot{\gamma}$ the shear rate (s⁻¹), C the flow consistency index (Pa•s ^{n}) and n the power law index (–).

In addition, viscosity as function of temperature can be described by the WLF-equation:

$$\log \left[\frac{\eta_T}{\eta_{T_g}} \right] = \log[a_T] = \frac{-C_1(T - T_g)}{C_2 + T - T_g} \quad (2)$$

With η_T and η_{T_g} complex viscosity (Pa•s) at temperature T and T_g (K) respectively, a_T a shift factor (–) and C_1 (–) and C_2 (K) material-dependent coefficients (Acierno and Patti, 2023).

Moreover, the effect of plasticisation with glycerol on the T_g of protein-based composites can be described with the Gordon-Taylor equation (3):

$$T_g = \frac{T_{g,pl} \cdot \omega_{pl} + k \cdot T_{g,pr} \cdot \omega_{pr}}{\omega_{pl} + k \cdot \omega_{pr}} \quad (3)$$

With T_g , $T_{g,pl}$, and $T_{g,pr}$ (K) the midpoint temperature of the glass transition for a protein-plasticiser blend, plasticiser or protein respectively and with ω_{pl} and ω_{pr} the mass fraction (–) of plasticiser and protein respectively (Skrdla et al., 2017). The Gordon-Taylor constant k (–) is inversely proportional to the plasticising effect of the plasticiser on the protein.

2.3. Estimation of shear rate in nozzle, pressure drop and extruder force

By estimating the pressure drop experienced by composites during extrusion through a nozzle, the necessary extrusion force can be calculated (see Eqs (4)–(8)). This information is useful in determining the processability of the composites using FDM.

During FDM, the volumetric output of the extruder screw per unit of time needs to match the required flow rate, to avoid under or over-extrusion during FDM. As many materials have shear dependent viscosities, it is important to establish the relation between the materials' shear thinning properties and its flow rate. The Rabinowitsch-corrected

shear rate $\dot{\gamma}$ (s^{-1}) in a cylindrical capillary during extrusion is given by:

$$\dot{\gamma} = \frac{Q}{\pi R^3} \frac{3n+1}{n} \quad (4)$$

With Q the flow rate (m^3/s), R the nozzle radius (m) and n the power law index (–) (Duty et al., 2018). The pressure drop across the nozzle for power-law liquids can be described by the modified Poiseuille equation:

$$\Delta P = \frac{2LC}{R} \left(\frac{Q}{\pi R^3} \frac{3n+1}{n} \right)^n \quad (5)$$

with ΔP the pressure drop (Pa), L the length of the nozzle bore (m), η the viscosity (Pa•s), L the nozzle length (m), Q the flow rate (m^3/s) and R the nozzle radius (m) (Chhabra and Richardson, 2011; Schutyser et al., 2018). Here we assume fully developed laminar flow and no slip conditions at the wall of the nozzle. The distribution of flow rate and pressure over the radius of the nozzle can be further defined by defining a friction factor and Reynolds number, but this is beyond the scope of this article. As long as the pressure drop over the nozzle for a desired flow rate Q is lower than the maximum system pressure, flow rate Q can be achieved (Duty et al., 2018). The maximum system pressure can be calculated according to

$$\Delta P = \frac{F}{A} \quad (6)$$

with A the cross sectional area of the screw (Chaunier et al., 2018). The theoretical maximum force F (N) that can be provided by the motor is given by:

$$F = \frac{T G}{r} \quad (7)$$

With T the holding torque (N•m), G the gear ratio (–) and r (m) the radius of the drive gear.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Preparation of plasticiser-protein composites

Composites manufactured through blending of protein and plasticiser yielded powder mixtures with poor flowability. This resulted in uneven flow rates of feed material to the extrusion screw resulting in uneven extrudate flow. A solvent casting method was adopted to improve the homogeneity of protein/plasticiser blends and with that the consistency of the extrudate flow. After grinding, free-flowing pellet was obtained which can be either directly 3D printed using the pellet-fed FDM printer. Production of composite filament was attempted. However, due to brittleness of the filament, this processing route was not further pursued in the current work.

The composite materials were prepared through i) protein dissolution and plasticisation; ii) film casting, evaporation and iii) pelletizing (see Fig. 1). Specifically, zein powder (Z3625, Sigma Aldrich, $\leq 8\%$ water) was dissolved in 96% ethanol (VWR chemicals). To fully dissolve the protein, the zein solution was heated to 60 °C and stirred at 200 RPM for a duration of 2 h on a hot plate. Spray-dried calcium caseinate (CaCas) (FrieslandCampina) was dissolved in demineralized water at room temperature while stirring at 200 RPM for 2 h. Blends of zein and CaCas were dissolved in 96% ethanol. Bidistilled glycerol (24388, VWR chemicals) was added to the protein solutions as the plasticiser. After dissolution, the composites were cast into films of 1–2 mm thickness in rimmed silicone sheets. Zein composites were dried at ambient temperature in a fume hood for 96 h. CaCas-composites were dried in an oven at 55 °C for 48 h. Dried films were ground using a spice grinder (Waring Commercial) and sieved through a 3 mm mesh sieve. Obtained pellets were stored in airtight containers prior to further analysis. The concentration of glycerol in the protein-based composite material ranged from 0% w/w to 35% w/w.

3.2. Rheological measurements

Rheological properties of the plasticised protein composite materials were analysed by CCR (RPA Elite by TA instruments), including critical strain as well as temperature- and frequency-dependent complex

Fig. 1. Schematic overview of the processes used to fabricate thermoplastic protein-based composite materials for fused deposition modelling. Pellets were produced by following the steps outlined in this schematic. Pellets can be used as the feedstock in pellet-fed FDM process to directly print 3D structures or to produce filament.

viscosity. We assumed the Cox-Merz rule is valid for our data and can be used to determine steady shear viscosity from complex viscosity (Chaunier et al., 2017a).

For each CCR measurement, a 4.15 ± 0.05 g aliquot of pellet was sandwiched between two layers of polyester film and positioned in the CCR's cavity before the chamber was sealed at a pressure of 4 bar. The procedure used to analyse the CCR data is provided in the Supplementary Materials, section 2.

3.2.1. Determination of critical strain using oscillatory strain sweep

In the linear viscoelastic regime (LVR) the viscoelastic properties of a material are strain independent. This independency is lost above a critical strain (C^*), where the microstructure of the material is changed as result of deformation. For polymers, critical strain increases with temperature and decreases with frequency (Whitcomb, 2023).

The critical strains of all plasticised protein composite materials were determined through strain sweeps, performed at the lowest temperatures relevant for FDM, being 100°C for CaCas composites and 110°C for zein composites. The strain during strain sweeps was increased from 0.1 to 128 % at a constant frequency of 10 Hz. The strain at which the storage modulus (G') was equal to 90 % of its plateau value was defined as the critical strain (Whitcomb, 2023).

3.2.2. Shear rate dependency of complex viscosity

The complex viscosity as a function of shear rate was determined by performing strain sweeps corresponding to shear rates from 0.02 to 80 s^{-1} at a constant frequency of 10 Hz and a temperature of 100°C for CaCas composites and 110°C for zein composites. The experimental data was fitted to the power law model (see Eq. (1)).

3.2.3. Temperature dependency of complex viscosity

The strain was kept below the critical strain to eliminate influence of shear on viscosity. Complex viscosity data was recorded while the samples were heated from their T_g to 140°C (zein) or 160°C (CaCas). The material-dependent coefficients C_1 and C_2 were computed by minimising the sum of squares difference between the experimentally obtained value of $\log[a_T]$ and the value calculated using C_1 and C_2 (equation (2)). We fit the data from T_g to $T_g+40^\circ\text{C}$ as WLF is not valid

below T_g and to prevent influence of thermal degradation. In short, we used the Solver function in excel to minimise: $L_2 = \sum_{T_g}^{T_g+40} \left(\log \left[\frac{\eta_T}{\eta_{T_g}} \right] - \frac{-C_1(T-T_g)}{C_2+T-T_g} \right)^2$

3.3. Determination of glass transition temperature using mDSC

Glass transition temperatures were determined by mDSC on a DSC250 (TA Instruments). For this analysis, samples were sealed in non-hermetic, aluminium pans. The thermal analysis profile included an initial heating step from 20°C to 180°C at a rate of $15^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to evaporate any free moisture in the samples, followed by equilibration at 20°C . Next, temperature modulation was enabled with an amplitude of 1.27°C and a period of 60 s. During a second heating step the temperature was increased to 180°C (zein) or 220°C (CaCas) at a rate of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. Above these temperatures rapid thermal degradation of proteins occurs (see Table 1 in Supplementary Materials) (Arrieta et al., 2013; Selling, 2010).

The T_g was determined as the inflection point of the shifted part of the thermograph (i.e. a shift in the baseline of the reversing heat flow signal), using the data obtained during the second heating cycle. We determined the exact temperature at which the inflection occurred with the 'glass transition' analysis function of TRIOS software (v5.6.0.87, TA instruments), selecting an analysis range of 30°C under and over the visually apparent T_g in the thermograph.

The experimentally determined T_g values were fitted to the Gordon-Taylor equation (see Eq. (3)). We used $T_{g,pl} = -83^\circ\text{C}$ for glycerol (Enrione et al., 2010; Schröter and Donth, 2000; Sou et al., 2011; Zondervan et al., 2007) and $T_{g,pr}$ of pure zein and calcium caseinate as determined by mDSC as input for the model fitting. Values for k were determined by minimising the residual sum of squares between measurement data and model prediction for miscible protein-plasticiser blends using the solver add-in in Microsoft Excel.

3.4. Pellet-fed 3D printing

A commercial FDM printer was modified to enable pellet-fed FDM. A

Table 1

Digital images of ring-shaped 3D-printed structures of plasticised proteins using fused deposition modelling and a pellet extruder as the printing nozzle.

Formulation	Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)		Printing speed (mm/s)		
	Heating block	Build plate	13	17	29
Zein80/Gly20	145	60			
Zein70/CaCas10/Gly20	145	70			
			34	41	57
Zein60/CaCas20/Gly20	165	70			

* The designed ring-shaped structure has an inner diameter of 14 mm. At a printing speed of 13 mm/s the screw speed equals 2 rpm.

single-screw extruder with a 6.25:1 length/diameter (L/D) ratio (MAHOR PX0850 v4, Spain) was mounted on the toolhead of a Felix Tec 4c 3D printer controlled through Repetier firmware (Felixprinters, The Netherlands). The extruder was driven by a Nema 17 bipolar stepper motor with a 5.18:1 planetary gearbox (17HS19-1684S-PG5). A resistive heating element inside an aluminium heating block converts power to heat, which the block transfers to the extruder barrel. The block was installed close to the nozzle (Fig. 1).

A hollow cylinder with an inner diameter of 14 mm, height of 5 mm and wall thickness of 2.4 mm as well as a cone with a height of 10 mm, wall angle of 45° and wall thickness of 2.4 mm were designed using Solidworks 2021. Printer instructions (gcode) were generated using Orcaslicer V2.1.0. A 0.8 mm line width and a concentric print pattern were used, so objects were printed as 3 concentric circles per layer. Full slicer profiles can be found in Table 3 in the Supplementary Materials.

The build plate temperatures were set (and recorded) on the printer, just below the glass transition temperature of the composites to improve bed adhesion and minimise the thermal gradient within the printed object to minimise deformation due to uneven shrinkage (warping). For composites that did not stick to the build plate, 3DLAC (Laiseven cosmetics) was used as adhesive on the build plate. Heating block temperature was chosen based on temperature sweep tests and increased to compensate for limited residence time of materials in the heated zone.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Glass transition temperatures of protein composites

Fig. 2A shows the glass transition temperatures values of zein plasticised with glycerol. The values for pure zein powder were determined to be 158 ± 2 °C, which is close to the value of 164 °C reported by Di Gioia et al. (1999). A small thermal transition was observed at around 96 °C on the thermogram of pure zein (Appendix, DSC section). Zhang et al. (2022) found a T_g of 93 °C for α -zein having a 7 % moisture content.

The small thermal transition we observed is thus most likely due to the presence of α -zein.

As expected, the glass transition temperatures of zein-based composites decreased with increasing glycerol content. At higher plasticiser concentrations ($\omega_{pl} \geq 0.125$) instead a discontinuity is observed. At the same time, the glass transitions become wider (see Fig. 9 in Supplementary Materials). Both observations are likely to be caused by the limited miscibility between zein and glycerol, which causes phase separation at higher glycerol concentrations. Whilst being a plasticiser, glycerol has limited miscibility with zein (Chaunier et al., 2017b; Rowat et al., 2021). At concentrations higher than its miscibility glycerol rich domains in a zein matrix will be created (Renzetti et al., 2021). Gontard and Ring (1996) reported that increasing levels of plasticiser in wheat gluten films resulted in broadening of the dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) $\tan \delta$ peaks, which was attributed this to the limited miscibility between the protein and the plasticiser. In the same study, good correspondence of T_g determined by DSC and DMTA was found. Pommet et al. (2003) reported a limited compatibility between plasticiser and protein evidenced by DSC.

We observed the development of a liquid film on the surface of dried zein sheets, providing further evidence for the separation of glycerol from the zein matrix. Due to strong intermolecular and intramolecular attractions in zein molecules, glycerol may be forced out of the zein matrix during drying.

Fig. 2B shows the glass transitions of CaCas-based composites as affected by glycerol. The T_g of pure CaCas powder was determined to be 208 ± 3 °C, very close to the T_g of anhydrous rennet casein at 206 °C as reported by Bengochea et al. (2007). The glass transition temperature decreased fairly linearly with the concentration of glycerol. Based on these results caseinate and glycerol appear to be well miscible. From sorption isotherms in literature it is evident that the hydrophilicity of calcium caseinate is higher than that of zein (Rüegg and Moor, 1984; Tillekeratne and Easteal, 2000). Yet, phase separation was observed after storage of CaCas-based samples with $\omega_{pl} \geq 0.35$ for a week (data

Fig. 2. Midpoint glass transition temperature (T_g) of samples determined by modulated differential scanning calorimetry: (a) zein (Zei) and (b) calcium caseinate (CaCas) plasticised with different concentrations of glycerol (gly), and (c) Zei/CaCas blends plasticised with 20 % w/w of glycerol. Dashed lines in (a) and (b) indicate fitting results using the Gordon Taylor equation; dashed line in (c) indicates the calculated T_g of Zei/CaCas blends based on their mass ratio of zein and CaCas.

not shown). Due to the glassy matrix, mass transfer occurred at a low rate. At $\omega_{pl} \geq 0.40$ the composites have a T_g below room temperature, and thus are in the rubbery state. This means that these materials fail the material requirements for FDM.

The effects of glycerol on the T_g of zein (up to $\omega_{pl} = 0.125$) and CaCas composites were effectively described by the Gordon-Taylor equation. The fitting parameter k was found to be 0.63 for zein-based ($R^2 = 0.97$) and 0.49 for CaCas-based ($R^2 = 0.98$) composites, respectively. The slightly higher fitting parameter k for the zein-glycerol system could be indicative of a somewhat lower plasticising effect of glycerol on zein (Kalichevsky et al., 1993). We expect that this is related to the lower compatibility of the hydrophilic glycerol with the hydrophilic regions within zein. Casein is more hydrophilic and therefore has better compatibility with glycerol.

Moreover, blending zein and CaCas could result in composite materials with intermediate properties, and may mitigate the miscibility issues between glycerol and zein. By varying the mass ratio between zein and CaCas, protein composites containing 80 % w/w protein and 20 % w/w glycerol were obtained. The glass transition temperatures of these blends are the weighted average of the T_g values of the two components (i.e. zein 80 %-gly 20 % and CaCas 80 %-gly 20 %) (Fig. 2C). This linear relation allows possible interpolation of the glass transitions over the whole range of zein/CaCas blends tested in this study and provides evidence the materials are well mixed.

4.2. Rheological properties of protein composites

4.2.1. Critical strain determined by amplitude strain sweep

The storage modulus G' and loss modulus G'' of the protein composites were measured using amplitude strain sweeps. Both G' and G'' remained constant until a critical strain is reached. Zein- and CaCas-based composites both showed strain softening above a critical strain, and the measured critical strain increases with plasticiser content (see Fig. 3). The same kind of strain softening behaviour was also reported for plant proteins plasticised with water, which is a known phenomenon in polymer flow (Van Der Sman et al., 2023; Whitcomb, 2023). It is noteworthy that the critical strain was low (~ 1 %) at plasticiser contents relevant for use in FDM ($W_{pl} \approx 0.2$, to avoid phase separation associated with higher W_{pl}). This implies that strain softening of the printing material is likely to occur during FDM. The decrease of G' , G'' and the complex viscosity due to strain softening at higher shear could be beneficial for the FDM printing process because a lower extrusion force will be needed.

Fig. 3. Critical strain of zein- and CaCas-based composites as a function of glycerol content (W_{pl} (-)) as determined by amplitude strain sweep tests.

4.2.2. Shear dependency of viscosity

During FDM, polymer materials flow under shear. In this study, we used Eq. (4) to estimate the Rabinowitsch-corrected shear rate for composites flowing through the nozzle of the pellet extruder. With $R = 4.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m and $Q = 3.3 \cdot 10^{-9}$ m³/s (a representative setting chosen for our printing experiments, see Section 4.3), we found a Rabinowitsch-corrected shear rate of 79 s⁻¹, which is in line with literature. Shear rate values of 40–200 s⁻¹ for a nozzle with bore size of 0.3 mm (Gilmer et al., 2018) and 30–100 s⁻¹ for a nozzle with bore size of 0.76 mm (Ajinjeru et al., 2017) were reported before. Materials used for FDM often show shear dependency of viscosity. Here, we determined the shear viscosity of protein composites under relevant conditions to better understand their behaviour. The shear rate range tested was up to 100 s⁻¹ (set according to the estimated Rabinowitsch-corrected shear rate).

The power law model (Eq. (1)) was used to describe the shear viscosity of protein composites formulated in this study (Fig. 4). The power law model was able to describe the viscosity from 1 s⁻¹ to 100 s⁻¹ for CaCas-based samples (see Fig. 4A for results of a representative sample). Nevertheless, only part of the viscosity data of zein-based samples was fitted to the power law model (see Fig. 4B for results of a representative sample).

Fig. 4C shows the consistency index C and power law index n of samples containing different levels of glycerol. For both zein- and CaCas-based samples, consistency index decreased as the concentration of glycerol increased. Interestingly, after an initial drop, the consistency index seems to have reached a plateau value when more plasticiser is added (Fig. 4C). The addition of plasticisers can reduce intermolecular interaction between polymer chains and increase free volume in the network because they insert in between polymer molecules and form secondary bonds (e.g. hydrogen bonds) with the polymer chains (Arrieta et al., 2013; Eslami et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2023). This reduction in bond strength between polymer chains lowers the yield stress of a material, which explains the lower consistency index. However, as more plasticiser is added, fewer polymer-polymer interactions remain and the reduction of intermolecular polymer interactions by adding more plasticiser will become less effective.

Furthermore, the power law index n was found to be lower than 1 for all tested samples, indicating shear thinning properties (Fig. 4C). Shear thinning behaviour of a material is a result of internal structure changing during flow. At rest, the polymer molecules conform to the most thermodynamically favourable structure, which in a network is often a coiled up confirmation to minimise exposure of their hydrophobic/philic groups to the surrounding. Under shear, these coils are stretched out and disentangled whilst hydrogen bonds are broken, allowing the polymer molecules to align with the flow. This reduces the overall resistance of the material to flow, which can be observed as shear-thinning behaviour with decreasing viscosity at higher shear rates. Here, we observed increasing glycerol content resulted in an increase in the shear thinning index, indicating the sample became less shear thinning. Most likely, the addition of plasticiser reduces unfavourable exposure of the side-chains to the environment. Therefore, the alignment effect caused by shear (inducing laminar flow) is also reduced, resulting in a reduction in the power-law index of the protein composites.

It is interesting to compare the shear thinning properties of our protein composites with some common materials used for FDM. Values reported in literature for the consistency index C and power law index n of common 3D printing polymers vary widely, for acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene (ABS) $n = 0.27$ – 0.51 and $C = 6.7$ – 12.2 kPa·s ^{n} and for polylactic acid (PLA) $C = 2.9$ kPa·s ^{n} and $n = 0.32$ – 0.68 at printing temperatures (Chen and Smith, 2021; Sanchez et al., 2019). This large spread of fitting parameters could be because different additives are included in the filaments by manufacturers. For a zein composite with 20 % glycerol we find $C = 4.7$ kPa·s ^{n} and $n = 0.57$ (–) at 110 °C (Fig. 4B), which are within the range of values commonly reported for FDM plastics. Therefore we expect it is feasible to use this material for

Fig. 4. Complex viscosity as function of shear rate measured by CCR for CaCas (A) and Zein (B) sample each plasticised with 20 % glycerol, and their fit using power law. C: Consistency index C and power law index n (parameters of power law fit) as function of glycerol content for zein and CaCas plasticised with glycerol. Dashed lines drawn to guide the eye.

FDM.

4.2.3. Temperature dependency of viscosity

During FDM, material flow is induced by extruding the printing material at elevated temperatures. The viscosity of a material should be low enough at the printing temperature so the motor can push the material out of the nozzle. Previously, a viscosity value of 0.2 kPa·s has been suggested as a target for material to have good printability and bonding after deposition (Spoerk et al., 2017). The temperature-dependent behaviour was determined for zein- and CaCas-based composites and a zein-CaCas blend (Fig. 5). At a glycerol concentration of 20 %, the complex viscosity of all three samples decreased as the temperature increased (Fig. 5A). Zein composite with 20 % glycerol reached a viscosity of 0.2 kPa·s at 135 °C. Furthermore, this sample had $G'' > G'$ over a wide temperature range, which means viscous behaviour is dominant. CaCas- and protein-blend-based

composites did not reach a viscosity lower than 1 kPa·s even when heated to 150 °C. Additionally, these samples had $G' > G''$, meaning solid-like behaviour is dominant under the tested conditions.

The viscosity of CaCas-based composites can be further reduced by increasing the temperature. However, thermal degradation of CaCas starts at 198 °C (Arrieta et al., 2013). We observed darkening of the colour of CaCas-based composites when the maximum measuring temperature was set to 180 °C or above in the mDSC. Similar colour change was also observed during extrusion experiments. Thermogravimetric analysis of protein composites confirmed this observation was caused by thermal degradation of protein (see Table 1 and Fig. 1 of Supplementary Materials). Adding more glycerol, up to 35 % w/w, could reduce the viscosity of CaCas-based composites without causing phase separation. Even then, the viscosity of CaCas-based composites did not meet the 0.2 kPa·s target at the maximum processing temperature. This implies that CaCas-based composites were not suitable for FDM. Indeed, in the

Fig. 5. A: Complex viscosity of Zein80Gly20, Zein40Ca40Gly20 and Ca80Gly20 samples as function of temperature. B: Storage modulus (G' , dashed line) and loss modulus (G'' , dotted line) as function of temperature for of Zein80Gly20, Zein40Ca40Gly20 and Ca80Gly20 samples.

current work FDM of CaCas was only found feasible when combining it with zein to achieve blend with sufficiently low T_g and viscosity (see section 4.3).

The temperature-dependent viscosity of concentrated polymers can be described with Williams–Landel–Ferry equation (Eq. (2)). Here, we took the η_{T_g} of each formulation as the measured viscosity at the corresponding T_g determined calorimetrically for the model fitting, instead of using the universal value of $\sim 10^{12}$ Pa·s (see Fig. 2). The fitting parameters $C_1 = 4.02$ K and $C_2 = 79.3$ K in the modified WLF model were obtained for our protein composites (Fig. 6). These values deviate from the ‘universal values’ of $C_1 = 17.44$ and $C_2 = 51.6$ K reported for synthetic polymers (Williams et al., 1955). The authors of the WLF model advise against using these universal values unless no other data is available. Previous studies also have reported material specific values for C_1 and C_2 (Barra and Mitchell, 2013; Maidannyk and Roos, 2016). It seems the WLF model could potentially be used to predict the viscosity of protein composites containing different amount of glycerol at temperature slightly above T_g (Williams et al., 1955). To translate these results to high-shear conditions (that are relevant for FDM processes), several authors have captured the effects of shear and temperature on viscosity of polymer using a single equation by applying the Cross-WLF or Bird-Carreau theory (Coogan and Kazmer, 2019; Le et al., 2021; Xia et al., 2018). However, this requires the determination of the zero-shear viscosity of the material, which is out of the scope of this study.

4.3. 3D printing of protein composites using pellet extrusion

In this study, protein composites were formulated to match the printability window of commonly used materials for FDM (e.g. PLA and ABS). Specifically, the T_g of zein composite with 12.5 % glycerol was similar to that of PLA (58 °C), whereas T_g of CaCas composite containing 20 % w/w glycerol was similar to that of ABS (108 °C) (Rowat et al., 2021). To demonstrate the feasibility of using protein composites as materials for FDM, we 3D printed several selected formulations with a pellet-fed FDM printer at different printing conditions (see Table 1). The results show that by adjusting the printing speed (i.e. indirectly the shear rate of extrusion), cylinders with good shape fidelity were obtained. The highest shape fidelity was achieved for a zein composite with 20 % glycerol printed at 145 °C and 13 mm/s. CaCas-containing formulations required a higher printing temperature and speed to be printed successfully due to its increased viscosity as discussed before.

At the printing speed of 13 mm/s the shear rate in the nozzle equals 79 s^{-1} (Eq. (4)). With the power law (fitting parameters in Fig. 4), the viscosity at this shear can be calculated at the strain sweep temperature. Utilizing the WLF relation with the C_1 and C_2 values obtained (Fig. 6), and the viscosity obtained in the last step, the viscosity at 145 °C and shear rate of 79 s^{-1} can be calculated. Thus we find that the viscosity at the optimized printing settings equals 141 Pa s, quite close to the

viscosity target of 200 Pa s (Spoerk et al., 2017).

Moreover, a structure with overhangs was successfully 3D-printed (see Fig. 8) which has not been reported in previous work on printing of zein composite (Chaunier et al., 2020; Thadasack et al., 2023). A cone shape with a 45° slope outer wall was printed using zein-based composite. It is generally accepted that FDM plastics such as ABS and PETG can be printed with overhangs up to 45°. The dimensions of the printed object were slightly different from the design at a wall thickness of 2.8 mm and a slope of 36–40° (see Fig. 7 a2). Nevertheless, these results demonstrate the excellent potential of protein composites as feedstock for FDM.

4.3.1. Estimation of shear rate and pressure drop

Equations (4)–(8) can be used to calculate the pressure drop over the nozzle. In the working range of 0–10 RPM (printing conditions in Table 1) the maximum achievable torque is 1.95 N m according to the torque curve provided by the manufacturer, lower than the theoretical maximum of 2.7 N m (Eq. (8)). The maximum system pressure is therefore 0.23 MPa.

Fig. 7. Photographs of FDM 3D printed structures. A1: hollow cylinder, 14 mm inner diameter, 5 mm height & 2.4 mm thick walls. A2: hollow cylinder with 45° overhang angle design, 100 mm height & 2.4 mm thick wall.

Fig. 6. Temperature-dependent viscosity of different formulations of protein composites as described by a Williams–Landel–Ferry equation (Eq. (2)): dashed and dotted lines represent experimental data and black line represents WLF fit.

Fig. 8. State diagram for zein-glycerol composites with iso-viscosity lines for the linear viscoelastic regime. Measurement data indicated with square markers.

For the extrusion of Zein80/Gly20 at optimal printing speed of 13 mm/s (Table 1) at 145 °C the pressure drop is 0.11 MPa (full calculation in Supplementary Material, section 3). As this is lower than the maximum system pressure, the zein composite can be extruded with the desired flow rate. For a CaCas/Gly20 composite at a printing speed of 13 mm/s at 165 °C (higher temperatures induced browning) the pressure drop is 1.9 MPa, higher than the maximum system pressure. It was expected that this material would not extrude, which was confirmed experimentally as the motor would stall during FDM of this composite.

4.3.2. Isoviscosity diagram

An isoviscosity diagram summarizes our data for zein-based composites (Fig. 8). Measurement values for T_g and several viscosities are indicated with dashed lines. In summary, viscosity at T_g is too high for extrusion. With increasing temperature and reduction of solids content, we arrive at the isoviscosity line of $\eta^* = 5000$ Pa s where extrusion is possible but adhesion and flowability are too poor for FDM. The Dahlquist criterion states that a material's G' should be < 0.1 MPa to enable good contact with other surfaces, which could be another evaluation point. With further increase of temperature and reduction of solids content we arrive at the isoviscosity line of $\eta^* = 200$ Pa s which is ideal for FDM. Finally, at $\eta^* = 100$ Pa s the material becomes too liquid for FDM and no self-support structure can be created after extrusion from the nozzle. This diagram can be transformed to account for shear-thinning effects at shear rates relevant to FDM by utilizing material-specific power-law fitting parameters. In summary, good printing performance of a composite can be adjusted by changing its formulation (e. g. type and concentration of protein and plasticisers) and processing conditions during FDM (e.g. print temperature and extrusion rate).

5. Conclusions

In this study, we successfully formulated protein-glycerol composites which showed similar thermal and rheological properties as conventional polymers used for FDM processes. The printability windows of materials were derived from their thermorheological properties. Selected formulations were 3D printed using a pellet-fed FDM printer

and showed good printability. Complex designs, such as a 3D structure with 45° overhangs, were realized. The development of protein-based composite materials extends the choice of materials for FDM. Such materials could potentially be used in 3D food printing and bioprinting across different applications. Future study could focus on testing different types of proteins and plasticisers and further exploring their applications. The pellet printing process could be further optimized by introducing a heated chamber to better control the temperature and thus printing performance of composite materials.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Quinten Steffens: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Marije Vliet:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ruud van der Sman:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Remko Boom:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Lu Zhang:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare there are no conflicts of interest.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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